

Ab initio study of hydrogen storage in lithium grafted metal-graphyne framework

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Hydrogen holds the promise to replace the widespread dependency on fossil fuels due to its renewable and pollution free nature. Metal-graphyne framework (MGF) constructed with magnesium oxide as a metal node and graphyne as a linker. Graphyne is a new 2D carbon allotrope connected with acetylenic linkages. Lithium is grafted on the graphyne linker of MGF. Density functional theory (DFT), with GGA-PBE exchange-correlation functional, is used to determine the geometric structures, their stability, binding strength of Li and graphyne of MGF, and hydrogen storage capacity. On full saturation with hydrogen, each Li atom physisorbs 3 H₂ molecules in the MGFLi₁₆ which results MGFLi₁₆-48H₂ system with a total gravimetric density of 7.2 wt.%. Further 12 more H₂ molecules could be accommodated in the pore space of MGFLi₁₆ and the resulting structure, MOFLi₁₆-60H₂ is obtained with hydrogen wt.% 8.9. The H₂ and Li interacted by Niu-Rao-Jena mechanism with average H-H bond distance enhanced up to 0.754 Å. The calculated sorption energies are found in the range of 0.36 to 0.21 eV. The molecular dynamics simulations reveal the stability of Li grafted MGF and the reversibility of adsorbed H₂ from the MGFLi₁₆-48H₂ system. The energetics and storage capacity meet the US DOE target which makes MGFLi₁₆ as a potential hydrogen storage material.

Keywords: Density functional theory, Li grafting, hydrogen storage, charge polarization, Born-Oppenheimer molecular dynamics.

Introduction

An everyday increase in the demand for energy and inadequate availability of energy resources makes hydrocarbon economy impractical. The conventional energy resources also release carbon dioxide which put an adverse effect on the environment^{1,2}. Thus, the limited availability of fossil fuels and their harmful effect on the environment increases interest in the scientific community to replace the conventional energy economy with the environmental friendly hydrogen economy^{1,3}. Hydrogen gas is considered as a carbonless economy as it is a clean and renewable carrier of energy¹⁻⁵. However, hydrogen is not freely available which makes it necessary to generate, store and transport it to the desired places for its further use in various applications. Presently, physical and materials-based techniques are used to store hydrogen^{2,3}. In physical based methods hydrogen is stored either in compressed form or in the form of liquified hydrogen. But these methods are not commercially feasible because they require expensive infrastructure and consume a large amount of energy during the storage. In material-based methods hydrogen can be stored in two ways viz.

physical adsorption and chemical adsorption^{2,3,6}. The storage of hydrogen via physical adsorption is found to be reversible which follows very fast kinetics as compared to the chemical adsorption pathway^{6,7}.

In recent years, a variety of materials have been studied and reported by several research groups which could be considered as hydrogen storage materials in the future. Nano porous materials such as carbon nanotubes⁸, graphene⁹, graphynes¹⁰⁻¹⁵ and fullerenes¹⁶ have been found to store hydrogen at ambient temperature and pressure conditions via associative manner. Several materials such as calix[n]-arenes^{5,17-19}, zeolites^{20,21}, metal-organic frameworks (MOFs)²²⁻²⁷, covalent-organic frameworks (COFs)^{28,29}, metal-inorganic frameworks^{30,31} and other materials^{32,33} have also been explored as potential hydrogen storage materials. The current research is focused on designing novel hydrogen storage materials to achieve the targets which are set by the U.S. Department of Energy (US DOE)³⁴.

Among all the proposed porous materials, MOFs are extensively studied as hydrogen storage materials due to the availability of large surface area which further provides a large

number of binding sites for hydrogen molecules^{35,36}. The objective of the present work is to design the metal-graphyne framework (MGF) by using magnesium oxide as a metal node and graphyne as a linker and explore the hydrogen storage capacity, reversibility and thermodynamic stability of Li grafted MGF. Graphyne is a 2D sheet of carbon allotrope first discovered by Baughman *et al.*¹⁰. In graphyne; benzene rings are connected by acetylenic linkages (-C-C≡C-C-). It is reported that metal decorated graphyne have been explored for hydrogen storage with high gravimetric density³⁸.

Recently, we designed and explored metal-graphyne framework consists of graphyne²⁷ linker decorated with lithium (MGF-Li₈) as a hydrogen storage material with the aid of density functional theoretical calculations. The computed molecular dynamics simulations results indicate the high reversibility of H₂ molecules in MGF-Li₈. Furthermore, the designed metal-graphyne framework decorated from one side with lithium are reported to store 6.4 wt% of hydrogen. In this work, the lithium is decorated on both sides of the metal-graphyne framework (MGF-Li₁₆) and studied the hydrogen storage capacity, reversibility and thermodynamic stability and the results are compared.

This paper is organized as follows: In next Section, computational details are presented. In the following Section, the results and discussions of hydrogen storage properties of Li grafted MGF are discussed. The summary and conclusions are provided in last Section.

Computational details

All the calculations are performed by density functional theory (DFT) with the spin-unrestricted method using the DMOL³ code^{39,40}. The Perdew-Burke-Ernzerhof (PBE) exchange-correlation functional within the spin-polarized generalized gradient-corrected approximation (GGA) is employed⁴¹. Double numerical basis set with polarization function (DNP) is adopted. The DFT-D (D stands for dispersion) approach with Grimme's van der Waals (vdW) correction term is used to determine the accurate description of weak interactions⁴². The real-space global orbital cutoff radius 5.2 Å is used for high quality results.

Energy parameters such as Li binding energy between Li and MGF, adsorption and desorption energy of adsorbed H₂ molecules, changes in bond lengths before and after the hydrogen adsorption, Hirshfeld charge analysis, thermody-

namics of usable hydrogen storage and Born-Oppenheimer molecular dynamics (BOMD)⁴³ simulations have been studied.

The binding energy of Li of MGFLi₁₆ is determined by the following equation^{44,45},

$$E_b = \frac{1}{16} \left[(16E_{Li} + E_{MGF}) - E_{MGFLi_{16}} \right] \quad (1)$$

where, $E_{MGFLi_{16}}$ is the total energy of MGFLi₁₆, E_{Li} energy of Li metal and E_{MGF} is the energy of MGF, respectively.

The average H₂ adsorption energy, E_{ad} is calculated by given equation^{44,45},

$$E_{ad} = \frac{1}{n} \left[(E_{MGFLi_{16} + nH_2}) - E_{MGFLi_{16} - nH_2} \right] \quad (2)$$

where E_{H_2} , $E_{MGFLi_{16} - nH_2}$, and n are the energy of H₂ molecule, the energy of MGFLi₁₆ and number of adsorbed hydrogen molecules.

To calculate the sequential desorption energy of adsorbed hydrogen molecules, the given equation is used,

$$E_{de} = E_{H_2} + E_{MGFLi_{16} - (n-1)H_2} - E_{MGFLi_{16} - nH_2} \quad (3)$$

where $E_{MGFLi_{16} - (n-1)H_2}$ is represented total energy of preceding H₂ molecules adsorbed on MGFLi₁₆-nH₂ system.

The practical usable hydrogen storage capacity has been determined by using chemical potential, μ at adsorbing (low temperature-high pressure) and desorbing (high temperature-low pressure) conditions. The thermodynamic usable hydrogen capacity is determined by calculating the occupation number (N_{use}) as,

$$N_{use} = \frac{\sum_{n=0}^{N_{Max}} n g_n \exp[n(\mu - E_{ad})/k_B T]}{\sum_{n=0}^{N_{Max}} g_n \exp[n(\mu - E_{ad})/k_B T]} \quad (4)$$

Here, N_{Max} , n , and g_n are the maximum numbers of adsorbed H₂ molecules per Li in MGFLi₁₆, a number of hydrogen molecules adsorbed and the configurational degeneracy of n , k_B is the Boltzmann constant, and E_{ad} represents the adsorption energy of hydrogen molecules stored in Li grafted MGF. The chemical potential, μ of gas phase H₂ at given pressure and temperature determined by the equation,

$$\mu = \mu_{ideal} - 0.00015(T - 186.5) + 0.00065[(\log P - 0.5)^2 - 0.25] \quad (5)$$

The gas phase chemical potential μ of H₂ gas as a function

of temperature and pressure is chosen from the experimental data^{46,47}.

The electron distribution and electron charge transfer mechanism are explained by using the Hirshfeld charge analysis. BOMD⁴³ simulations are performed to determine the stability of MGFLi₁₆ system, and the reversibility of adsorbed H₂ molecules from the Li grafted MGF. The BOMD simulations have been performed at the range of temperature with Γ -point sampling at 5 ps run time and 1 fs time-step. Canonical NVT ensemble uses with Nose thermostat to control the temperature during BOMD simulations.

Results and discussion

The structure of the MGF is optimized and provided in Fig. 1. MGF has been designed with graphyne linker and magnesium oxide as a metal node²⁷. Each graphyne linker of MGF is grafted with 4 Li atoms, two Li used from the top, and other two from the bottom side and the resulting structure MGFLi₁₆ is represented in Fig. 2a. Li atoms are used in their ground state configuration to graft the MGF. The average Li binding energy in MGFLi₁₆ is calculated by using eq. (1) and is found to be 2.68 eV, which indicate that Li atoms strongly bind with graphyne linker of MGF. In MGF, the distance between a diagonal metal node to metal node and between adjacent metal nodes are 24.45 Å and 17.33 Å respectively. The geometry of MGFLi₁₆ shows that the distance between a diagonal metal node to metal node and between adjacent metal nodes are increasing and is found to be 24.55 and 17.39 Å on Li grafting of MGF.

Fig. 1. Structure of metal-graphyne framework (MGF). Mg, C, H and O atoms are represented by green, dark grey, white and red colors respectively.

Structural changes on the adsorption of H₂ molecules in MGFLi₁₆

The H₂ molecules are subsequently introduced on each Li of optimized MGFLi₁₆. After optimization, it is observed that H₂ molecules on each Li in MGFLi₁₆-nH₂ system is adsorbed in a molecular manner with elongation in H-H bond distance up to 0.755 Å from its bare distance of 0.741 Å. On sequential adsorption of H₂ molecules shows that maximum three H₂ molecules is adsorbed on per Li in MGFLi₁₆ resulting MGFLi₁₆-16H₂, MGFLi₁₆-32H₂, and MGFLi₁₆-48H₂ systems. The H₂ adsorption cycle of MGFLi₁₆-nH₂ (where n = 16, 32, and 48) is represented in Fig. 2b-d. In Fig. 2a1, Li binding to the linker is shown enlarged. Similarly, in Fig. 2b1-d1, H₂ binding to the Li metals is shown enlarged. It is observed that all the H₂ molecules bind on each Li in MGFLi₁₆-nH₂ (where n = 16, 32, and 48) in molecular form. The H₂ molecules bind with Li in physisorbed fashion by Niu-Rao-Jena charge polarization mechanism^{48,49}. In charge polarization mechanism, charge generates on graphyne linker, shifts to the Li atoms, the charge on Li atoms polarizes the incoming H₂ molecules in the system; as a result, H₂ molecules bind in molecular form. The molecular adsorption indicates that all the H₂ molecules are physisorbed on MGFLi₁₆-nH₂.

The Li-Li distance of the top and bottom of each linker increases from 2.547 to 2.749 Å with the number of H₂ molecules in the system. The distance between a diagonal metal node to metal node and between adjacent metal nodes decreases on the adsorption of first H₂ molecule on each Li in the system while on adsorption of second and third H₂ molecules on each Li in the system, both the distances increases as shown in hydrogen adsorption cycle in Fig. 2b-d. The distance between Li and center of graphyne linker (Li-Gc), and between Li and adsorbed H (Li-H) increases with the number of hydrogen molecules adsorbed in the MGFLi₁₆-nH₂ (n = 16, 32, and 48) system. The distance between Li-Gc is found in the range of 1.273 to 1.374 Å for first to third H₂ molecule on each Li while the distance between Li-H ranges from 2.036 to 2.065 Å for first to third H₂ molecules adsorbed on each Li in the system. All the distances are provided in Table 1. The hydrogen wt.% is found to be 7.2 for MGFLi₁₆-48H₂ system, where each Li adsorbs 3 H₂ molecules via physisorption.

Fig. 2. Hydrogen sorption pathway of (a) MGFLi_{16} , (b) $\text{MGFLi}_{16}\text{-}16\text{H}_2$, (c) $\text{MGFLi}_{16}\text{-}32\text{H}_2$ and (d) $\text{MGFLi}_{16}\text{-}48\text{H}_2$ systems. Mg, C, H, O and Li atoms are represented by green, dark grey, white, red and purple colors respectively. For clarity, the enlarged images of linkers are shown in a1, b1, c1 and d1.

Table 1. The average bond distance between Li-Li from top and bottom of the graphyne linker in MGFLi_{16} , graphyne center of MGF and Li (Li-Gc), Li and physisorbed hydrogen distance (Li-H) and physisorbed hydrogen distance (H-H). All average distances are measured in Å

System	Li-Li	Li-Gc	Li-H	H-H
MGFLi_{16}	2.534	1.267	–	–
$\text{MGFLi}_{16}\text{-}16\text{H}_2$	2.547	1.273	2.036	0.755
$\text{MGFLi}_{16}\text{-}32\text{H}_2$	2.634	1.317	2.069	0.754
$\text{MGFLi}_{16}\text{-}48\text{H}_2$	2.749	1.374	2.065	0.755

The pore space of Li grafted framework is available for more hydrogen molecules storage. To increase the hydrogen storage capacity, 12 more H_2 molecules are introduced in the pore space of MGFLi_{16} , and the optimized resulting geometry of $\text{MGFLi}_{16}\text{-}60\text{H}_2$ is shown in Fig. 3. The hydrogen molecules in the pore space trapped with elongation in H-H bond distance. The calculated H wt.% is found to be 8.9 for $\text{MGFLi}_{16}\text{-}60\text{H}_2$.

Fig. 3. Optimized structure of $\text{MGFLi}_{16}\text{-}60\text{H}_2$. Mg, C, H, O and Li atoms are represented by green, dark grey, white, red, and purple colors respectively.

Energetic parameters

The binding strength of adsorbed H₂ and Li atom of MGFLi₁₆ system is explored by computing the average H₂ adsorption energy, E_{ad} , by using eq. (2). The adsorption energy values for first H₂ molecule adsorbed on each Li in MGFLi₁₆-nH₂ is found to be 0.36 eV. On further adsorption of second and third H₂ molecules on each Li results in MGFLi₁₆-32H₂ and MGFLi₁₆-48H₂ systems and the E_{ad} values are 0.32 and 0.28 eV, respectively for second and third H₂ molecule. The average adsorption energy for 12 more H₂ molecules trapped in the pore space of MGFLi₁₆-48H₂ is calculated and found between 0.28 to 0.25 eV for 49th to 60th H₂ molecule in the MGFLi₁₆-nH₂ (n = 49 to 60). The adsorption energy values for hydrogen molecules trapped in the pore space are provided in Table S1 in the Supporting Information. The adsorption energy values indicate that hydrogen molecules are adsorbed reversibly and these values are found in the desired range of target set by the DOE.

Further, to examine the reversibility of adsorbed H₂ from the Li grafted MGF, the subsequent desorption energy, E_{de} , is calculated by using eq. (3). The desorption energy values are 0.36, 0.29 and 0.21 eV, respectively for first, second and third hydrogen molecules adsorbed in MGFLi₁₆-nH₂ (n = 16, 24, and 48) system. The desorption energy values show that the adsorbed hydrogen molecules are easily detached from the Li grafted MGFLi₁₆-nH₂ systems. The average H₂ adsorption and subsequent desorption energy values are given in Table 2. These low values of both average hydrogen adsorption and subsequent desorption energies indicate that Li grafted MGF is reversible hydrogen storage material.

Table 2. The average adsorption (E_{ad}) and sequential desorption (E_{de}) energy of adsorbed H₂ molecules in MGFLi₁₆-nH₂ (where n = 16, 32, and 48) system. All energy values are given in eV

System	E_{ad}	E_{de}
MGFLi ₁₆	–	–
MGFLi ₁₆ -16H ₂	0.36	0.36
MGFLi ₁₆ -32H ₂	0.32	0.29
MGFLi ₁₆ -48H ₂	0.28	0.21

Hirshfeld charge analysis of MGFLi₁₆-nH₂

The charge transfer mechanism is explored by computing Hirshfeld charges on C atoms of graphyne linker of MGF, on Li atoms before and after hydrogen adsorption and

adsorbed hydrogen in the systems. The Hirshfeld charges are computed in e.u. and plotted in Fig. 4. The Hirshfeld charge values are 0.007, -0.015, -0.014, -0.013, and -0.012 e.u. respectively, for C atoms of graphyne linker of MGF, MGFLi₁₆, MGFLi₁₆-16H₂, MGFLi₁₆-32H₂, and MGFLi₁₆-48H₂ systems. The Hirshfeld charges on Li atoms are found to be 0.320, 0.239, 0.209, and 0.195 e.u. for Li grafted system and for first, second, and third hydrogen loaded system. Further, the charges on adsorbed hydrogen are 0.034, 0.021, and 0.015 e.u., respectively for first, second, and third hydrogen molecule adsorbed on each Li in the system. It is observed that charge on C atoms of graphyne linker increases up to -0.015 e.u. on Li grafting.

Fig. 4. Hirshfeld charges on C atom of graphyne linker, Li atom and adsorbed hydrogen of MGFLi₁₆-nH₂ system (where n = 16, 32, and 48).

The neutral Li donates electronic charge to the C of graphyne linker and gets positive charge on Li grafting MGF. The sequential adsorption of hydrogen molecules on each Li in the system shows Li gets an electronic charge from the C of graphyne linker and H of adsorbed hydrogen molecules. The Hirshfeld charge transfer indicates that the adsorbed hydrogen molecules bind with Li of MGFLi₁₆ by charge polarization mechanism.

Thermodynamic usable hydrogen capacity

To be a potential material for hydrogen storage, enough H₂ molecules should be adsorbed at storage conditions and these adsorbed H₂ molecules should be smoothly desorbed

Fig. 5. Snap-shots of BOMD simulations of $\text{MGFLi}_{16}\text{-48H}_2$ at the temperatures of (a) 300, (b) 350 and (c) 373 K.

from the material at desorption conditions. To determine the usable hydrogen capacity, the occupation number (N_{use}) has been calculated by using eq. (4). The operational conditions for H_2 adsorption at adsorption (30 atm and 298 K) and H_2 release at desorption conditions (3 atm and 373 K)^{47,48}.

The values of μ_{ideal} at 30 atm and 298 K is -0.21 eV which results in the μ value -0.22 eV. However, at 3 atm and 373 K, the μ_{ideal} value is -0.36 eV and the μ value is -0.38 eV. The calculated occupation number, N , is found to be 2.25 at adsorption conditions (30 atm and 298 K), and N is 0.31 at desorption conditions (3 atm and 273 K). So, the usable number, N_{use} , shows that 1.94 H_2 molecules per Li adsorbed at operational conditions in the Li grafted MGF with the practical H wt.% 5.3.

Molecular dynamics simulations of $\text{MGFLi}_{16}\text{-48H}_2$ system

BOMD simulations have been performed over three different temperatures 300, 350, and 373 K up to 5 ps run time with 1 fs time-step to understand the stability of MGFLi_{16} system and the reversible process of adsorbed hydrogen from the fully hydrogen saturated $\text{MGFLi}_{16}\text{-48H}_2$ system. The snap shots of BOMD simulations are provided in Fig. 5a-c at three different temperatures. The BOMD simulations at 300 K, indicating that hydrogen molecule starts releasing from the $\text{MGFLi}_{16}\text{-48H}_2$ system and one hydrogen molecule from each Li is detached from the system. Further, on increasing the simulation temperature up to 350 K, show that two hy-

drogen molecules are smoothly released from each Li of $\text{MGFLi}_{16}\text{-48H}_2$. The simulation at a higher temperature up to 373 K shows that all three hydrogen molecules desorbed from each Li of $\text{MGFLi}_{16}\text{-48H}_2$ system. The simulations at 373 K, shows that MGF structure is stable and the Li remains near the graphyne linker in the framework. Simulations at 373 K also show that there is no Li clustering. The study of BOMD simulations reveals that all the hydrogen molecules are adsorbed in a reversible manner which makes MGFLi_{16} as a potential material for hydrogen storage.

Conclusions

The hydrogen storage properties of Li grafted MGF has been explored by using first-principles density functional theory. The GGA-PBE functional along with DNP basis set has been used throughout the calculations. The Li-graphyne binding energy 2.68 eV show that Li strongly binds with graphyne linker of MGF making MGFLi_{16} system. Sequential introduction of hydrogen molecules on Li grafted MGF show that maximum 3 H_2 molecules are adsorbed on each Li in the system and the resulting structure $\text{MGFLi}_{16}\text{-48H}_2$ is obtained. The hydrogen molecules are adsorbed in a molecular manner by charge polarization mechanism indicates that all the hydrogen molecules adsorbed in physisorbed fashion. The calculated average adsorption and sequential desorption energy values are low and found in the range of target set by DOE, i.e. between 0.2–0.4 eV, which confirms that all the adsorbed H_2 molecules are reversible. Hirshfeld charge

analysis further proves that hydrogen molecules are adsorbed by the charge polarization mechanism proposed by Niu-Rao-Jena.

The practical usable hydrogen capacity is calculated as a function of temperature and pressure. The stability of MGFLi₁₆ and the release of adsorbed hydrogen molecules from MGFLi₁₆-48H₂ are examined by BOMD simulations at the temperature range between 300 to 373 K. BOMD simulations indicate that all the hydrogen molecules are liberated at 373 K. The simulations confirm that the structure of MGFLi₁₆ is stable up to 373 K which show that the Li grafted MGF can be reused to store the hydrogen molecules. The adsorbed wt.% is found to be 8.9 for hydrogen saturated MGFLi₁₆ system which is higher than earlier studied MGF decorated with eight Li atoms²⁷. The high weight % and low sorption values for Li decorated system makes it a potential hydrogen storage material.

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Supporting Information

Average H₂ adsorption energy of MGFLi₁₆-nH₂ (n = 49-60) are provided in Table S1. The internal coordinates of all the optimized geometries of MGF, MGFLi₁₆, MGFLi₁₆-nH₂ (n = 16, 32, 48, and 60) are provided in Tables S2-S6 in Supporting Information.

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